

Effect of the Dialogue and Argumentation Strategy on the Academic Achievement of Ordinary Level Students in Zimbabwe

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of the dialogue and argumentation strategy on the academic achievement of mathematics students studying the subject at ordinary level. The research strategy used was a descriptive survey. A quantitative approach that used a structured questionnaire for data collection from a sample of 100 O' level Mathematics teachers was used. Data validation was done using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used for data analysis. The empirical findings of the study indicated that all the factors of dialogue and argumentation strategy namely: collective teaching, purposeful teaching, supportive teaching, reciprocal teaching, cumulative teaching and pedagogical repertoires have a significant and positive influence on the teaching of ordinary level mathematics. These results demonstrate that the dialogue and argumentation strategy has a significant effect on the academic achievement of ordinary level mathematics students. The main study limitation was that the findings of this study might not be transferable nationally since the study was delimited to only schools in Gutu district of Masvingo province in Zimbabwe. These results have implications on the effective teaching of ordinary mathematics in secondary schools in Zimbabwe.

Keywords: *Academic performance, argumentation, collective teaching, cumulative teaching, dialogue, pedagogical repertoire.*

Suggested citation: Munyati, L., Rudhumbu, N. & Sunzuma, G. (2024). Effect of the Dialogue and Argumentation Strategy on the Academic Achievement of Ordinary Level Students in Zimbabwe. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 210-223. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2024.1(3).19

Introduction

Underachievement in Mathematics is a major worry because of the significance placed on the subject (Makamure, 2018). According to Jose (2015), mathematics is essential for finding solutions to issues in all subject areas. Worldwide, societies consider mathematics to be essential to the progression of science, technology, politics, and socioeconomics (Mutai, 2016). Mathematics is also an essential subject used worldwide in a wide range of professions, including natural science, engineering, medicine, finance, and the social sciences. This means that having excellent mathematical skills is essential for numerous job paths (Buibas & Stankous, 2015). Despite its importance, worldwide student achievement in mathematics remains low (Siew, 2018). In Zimbabwe there is growing national concern regarding the performance of ordinary level (O'level) mathematics students (Makamure, 2018). Underachievement in mathematics remains a big problem in Zimbabwe with currently no clear way to address it in Zimbabwe (Makamure, 2018).

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According to Richardson et al. (2015), one of the things that has a big impact on how well students perform in mathematics is the teachers' instructional strategies. Hence, dialogue and argumentation may have an impact on students' academic achievement in mathematics. Despite the fact that mathematics is an important subject in formal education and is closely related to human life, students' ability to solve mathematical problems through conversation and reasoning is still inadequate (Jailani et al., 2015; Makamure, 2018; Putra et al., 2018).

According to research, learning occurs most effectively when students participate in discourse that allows them to both engage in cognitive restructuring of their own understanding and knowledge and to reflect on their own thinking (Muhonen, 2018). When students are open to each other's perspectives and try to understand each other, it is known as shared thinking or educational discourse (Phillipson & Wegerif, 2017).

Engaging students in mathematical dialogue and argumentation has been encouraged by recent educational policy documents (e.g., the Mathematics Teaching and Learning Framework of 2018 in South Africa, the Common Core State Standards for Mathematics (CCSSM) of 2015 in the United States, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education (MoPSE) blueprint, 2016–2022, and Cyprus's Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC), 2015). The materials help students develop strong mathematical discussions and arguments and evaluate other people's reasoning. Mathematical dialogue and argumentation is a strategy defined by Langrall and Rumsey (2016) as a dynamic social conversation process in order to find new Mathematical concepts and convince others of a point of view. Mathematical justification is necessary to persuade other students that a Mathematical proposition is valid. This implies that in a classroom setting, students provide enough and respectable justifications to convince others of the truth of their claims, hence justifications are incorporated in mathematical arguments.

In order to generate mathematically adept students who can build strong arguments, evaluate the thinking of others, and ultimately perform better in mathematics, dialogue and argumentation essential (Arista et al., 2018).

Dialogue and argumentation is a discussion technique that, in accordance with Rapanta (2019), encourages and stimulates students' critical thinking. This implies that arguing is a part of dialogic teaching. Students become disinterested in mathematics when teachers present problems in a didactic manner in most courses (Buibas & Stankous, 2015). In order to increase academic accomplishment in mathematics classes at the regular level, mathematics teachers must discover variables affecting the effectiveness of mathematics instruction using a dialogue and argumentation technique. In order to raise the academic achievement of students studying mathematics at the ordinary level, this study set out to identify the factors that influence how well the subject is taught utilizing dialogue and argumentation approach. The study was directed by the subsequent objective: To identify the variables that affect how well mathematics is taught using dialogue and argumentation approach.

Literature review

This section discusses principles that influence the use of dialogue and argumentation approach in teaching and learning in general and in the teaching of O'level mathematics in secondary schools in particular. The principles or factors which include Collective Teaching (CT), Purposeful Teaching (PT), Supportive Teaching (ST), Reciprocal Teaching (RT), Cumulative Teaching (CUT) and Pedagogic Repertoire (PR), are used to inform hypotheses formulation in the study. A research model (Figure i) based on the dialogue and argumentation factors above, was developed.

Figure 1. Research model

Collective Teaching and Dialogue and Argumentation

Collective teaching (CT) involves the mathematics teacher and students work on educational tasks jointly rather than separately (Alexander, 2017). In this situation, the teacher interacts actively in dialogue and argumentation with the mathematics students. Separate studies by Aguilera et al. (2020), Alexander (2018), Han and Kang (2019) and Alexander et al. (2017) in their studies, found that student-student interaction through the use of collective teaching as part of dialogue and argumentation, assists students to collaboratively organise their thoughts, reflect on their thoughts, reflect on their understanding, find gaps in their reasoning and improve their performance in mathematics. Such a situation helps in the effective use of dialogue and argumentation. Based on the results of the previous research, the first hypothesis of this study is given as follows:

H1: There is a significant and positive relationship between Collective Teaching (CT) and effective use of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching O' level Mathematics students

Purposeful Teaching and Dialogue and Argumentation 2

Purposeful teaching (PT) involves the teacher planning and steering discussion with specific learning goals in mind (Alexander, 2017). This means that the teacher has certain learning goals in mind rather than the lesson being a 'free for all'. Choosing the right teaching strategy for a particular mathematical topic can really enhance the dialogue and argumentation by engaging and enthusing mathematics students to want to contribute more to the lesson. Studies by Davidson and Edwards-Groves (2018), Alexander (2017) and Lin (2018), found that purposeful teaching (PT) positively influences the effective use of dialogue and argumentation strategy when teaching goals that the teacher would have set for his /her lesson ensure that the learning of mathematics does not just become a more focused and motivating process. Based on the results of the previous research, the second hypothesis of this study is given as follows:

H2: There is a significant and positive relationship between Purposeful Teaching (PT) and effective use of Dialogic and Argumentation (DA) in the teaching O' level Mathematics students.

Supportive Teaching and Dialogue and Argumentation

Supportive teaching (ST) ensures that mathematics students can articulate their ideas freely with confidence due to an environment of support the teacher would have created for the effective teaching

of mathematics using the dialogue and argumentation strategy. Effective use of dialogue and argumentation occurs when the teacher creates a teaching environment where he or she is always available to support student learning and also where students are free and willing to help one another to achieve a shared understanding of mathematical concepts (Alexander, 2017). This therefore means that teaching and learning when using the dialogue and argumentation strategy, needs to be done in a supportive environment where everyone feels comfortable enough to contribute. This is a prerequisite for the effective use of dialogue and argumentation. Studies by Hennessy et al. (2019) and Alexander et al. (2017) found that increased emphasis on supportive teaching (ST) in mathematics classrooms help students to gain confidence and participate more effectively in the mathematics lessons ensuring effective use of dialogue and argumentation. Based on the results of previous research, the third hypothesis of this study is given below:

H₃: There is a significant and positive relationship between Supportive Teaching (ST) and effective use of Dialogic and Argumentation (DA) in the teaching O' level Mathematics students.

Reciprocal Teaching and Dialogue and Argumentation

Reciprocal teaching (RT) involves mathematics teachers and students listening to one another, sharing ideas, and considering alternative viewpoints (Alexander, 2017). This is in line with dialogic teaching that takes on a conversational structure where discussion and argumentation are used to probe and challenge mathematics students. Separate studies by Muhonen (2018), Guardian et al. (2016) and Atanga et al. (2017) showed that opportunities for students to engage each other in a reciprocal manner contribute to the effective use of the dialogue and argumentation strategy in the teaching of mathematics. Through reciprocal teaching, students are able to share mathematical knowledge and understand mathematics concepts better. Based on the results of previous research, the fourth hypothesis of this study is given as follows:

H₄: There is a significant and positive relationship between Reciprocal Teaching and effective use of Dialogic and Argumentation in the teaching O' level Mathematics students.

Cumulative Teaching of and Dialogue and Argumentation

Cumulative teaching (CUT) involves teachers, students learning by building on their own, others' ideas, and linking them to coherent lines of thinking and inquiry (Alexander, 2017). The above involves ongoing talk, with the teacher and students building on each other's contributions, weaving them into coherent and logical lines of enquiry and allowing for a deeper exploration of learning as part of using the dialogue and argumentation strategy. A study by Lee (2016) found that Cumulative Teaching (CUT) contributes to the effective use of dialogue and argumentation since it helps mathematics students to more effectively engage with as well as link previously learned mathematical concepts with current concepts the teacher would have exposed them to earlier. Based on the results of previous research, the fifth hypothesis of this study is given as follows:

H₅: There is a significant and positive relationship between cumulative teaching and effective use of Dialogic and argumentation in the teaching O' level Mathematics students.

Pedagogical Repertoire and Dialogue and Argumentation

Pedagogical repertoire (PR) consist of the techniques and activities that are used to suit both known and novel situations or address a particular purpose in the mathematics classroom (Muhonen, 2018). This means that pedagogical repertoire provides teachers with a platform to employ a host of strategies, activities and techniques in the teaching and learning of mathematics using dialogue and argumentation (DA) approach. A study by Alexander (2017) found that mathematics teachers who have a pedagogical repertoire have ability to develop in their students, confidence to tell and explain, ask different relevant questions, explore ideas, clearly articulate their responses as well as frame meaningful opinions and judgements on mathematical situations they will be dealing with. Based on the results of previous research, the sixth hypothesis of this study is given as follows:

H₆: There is a significant and positive relationship between pedagogical repertoire and effective use of Dialogic and argumentation in the teaching O' level Mathematics students.

Research Methodology

This section reports on the research design, paradigm, approach, methods and instruments used in the study. Descriptive survey research design was the chosen research strategy. Positivism research paradigm was used to guide knowledge production in the study. Pragmatism emphasises observable and measurable data as knowledge. A quantitative approach was employed in this study. The subjects of this study consisted of approximately 100 O' level Mathematics teachers at selected public high schools in Gutu district of Masvingo province. Stratified random sampling was used for selecting proportionate samples of participating teachers for this study. The sample consisted of 100 O' level Mathematics teachers from 12 schools in Gutu district of Masvingo province. 100 questionnaires were administered to the participating teachers. As part of administration, the researcher first obtained permission to carry out the research at the twelve secondary schools from the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education (MOPSE) of Zimbabwe before commencing data collection. Biographic profiles of the respondents are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Biographic Factors of O' Level Mathematics Teachers

Factor	Item	Number	%
Gender	Female	27	41
	Male	39	59
Age	<30 years	15	23
	31-40 years	26	39
	41-50 years	13	20
	> 50 years	12	18
Educational level	Certificate in Education (CE)	4	6
	Diploma in Education (Dip Ed)	15	23
	Bachelor's degree	35	53
	Master's degree	12	18
Years of teaching experience	≤10 years	21	32
	11-20 years	18	27
	21-30 years	16	24
	> 30 years	11	17

The results in Table 1 showed that schools have more male (59%) than female teachers teaching O' level Mathematics. Most of the teachers teaching Mathematics at Ordinary level have an undergraduate degree with very few (29%) being non-degreed. It is also shown from Table (i) that most of the teachers have 20 years and below years of teaching experience which also corresponds with the fact that most (52%) of teachers are below 40 years of age.

Instrument Development

A structured questionnaire with six sections that used a five-point Likert scale was developed for collecting data on factors influencing the effective teaching of mathematics using the dialogue and argumentation approach. The six sections were as follows: Collective Teaching (CT)- 5 items, Purposeful Teaching (PT)- 4 items, Supportive Teaching (ST)- 3 items, Reciprocal Teaching (RT)- 5 items, Cumulative Teaching (CUT)- 4 items, and Pedagogic Repertoire (PR)- 4 items.

Results

This section discusses data validation for the measurement scale as well as how data were analysed.

Validation of the Research Instrument

This portion established the reliability (internal consistency) and validity (convergent and discriminant) of the questionnaire data. The validation procedure involved the use of two tests. According to Hair et al. (2019), the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test is a measure of sample adequacy that was first used to determine whether Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) could be used to validate the data.

The KMO of .801 ($KMO \geq .05$) and the significant Bartlett's test of sphericity of 121.510 ($p = .000$) in Table ii indicate that the data structure is appropriate for conducting CFA on the questionnaire-collected data (Hair et al., 2010). In order to validate the data, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used as the second step in the validation procedure.

Table 2. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's Tests for Independent Variables and Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Test	Result
KMO Measure of sampling adequacy	.801
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: Approx. Chi Square	121.510
Df	51
Sig.	.000

Table 3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model constructs	Construct items	SFL ($\lambda > .6$)	CA ($\alpha > .7$)	CR (CR > .6)	AVE (AVE > .6)	Skewness (S < 2)	Kurtosis (K < 4)
Collective Teaching (CT)	CT2	.825	.901	.920	.712	1.447	1.771
	CT3	.819				0.920	2.544
	CT4	.713				1.337	3.099
Purposive Teaching (PT)	PT1	.800	.768	.811	.733	1.319	3.158
	PT2	.639				1.020	2.917
	PT3	.913				1.445	1.809
Supportive Teaching (ST)	ST1	.665	.813	.847	.692	0.802	2.713
	ST2	.827				1.162	3.006
Reciprocal Teaching (RT)	RT1	.901	.852	.861	.664	0.922	2.388
	RT 2	.755				1.075	2.518
	RT3	.815				1.306	2.117
Cumulative Teaching (CUT)	CUT2	.847	.815	.827	.692	1.429	2.190
	CUT3	.781				0.821	2.733
Pedagogic Repertoire (PR)	PR1	.911	.844	.766	.661	1.273	2.551
	PR2	.813				1.380	3.104
	PR3	.754				1.310	2.994
Dialogue and argumentation (DA)	DA1	.649	.892	.850	.691	1.005	2.118
	DA2	.781				1.017	3.011
Academic performance (AP)	AP1	.775	.803	.794	.704	.0937	1.820
	AP3	.810				1.229	3.003

Key: SFL - Standardized factor loadings; CA - Cronbach alpha; CR - Composite reliability; AVE - Average variance extracted.

The validity (convergent) and dependability of the data gathered with the instrument that was intended were established by Table iii. The data was first cleaned up by the researcher by eliminating anomalies. Finding outliers, or construct items with standard factor loadings of less than .6 ($< .6$), reliability coefficients of less than .7 ($\alpha < .7$), and average variance extracted of less than .6 ($AVE < .6$), was one step in the data cleaning process (Hair et al., 2017, 2019). The following questions were found to be outliers during the cleaning process and were removed from the final questionnaire: CT4, RT4, RT5, CUT1,

CUT4, PR4, DA3, and AP2. Following the cleaning procedure, the data was simultaneously checked for normalcy and validated.

Two metrics, namely Kurtosis and Skewness, were utilized to test the normalcy of the data. The data was confirmed to be normally distributed for all values $K < |4|$, as indicated by the kurtosis values, which varied between 1.492 and 3.214, meeting the minimum benchmark value of $K < |4|$ (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). The use of the Skewness metric in the test of normalcy further confirmed the data's normal distribution. For all values $S < |2|$, the skewness values ranged from .0720 to 1.447, indicating that the data was normally distributed (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). Since the data is regularly distributed, parametric tests—which are more reliable than non-parametric tests—may be used to test hypotheses, as suggested by Yu (2008), Corder and Foreman (2014), and Vickers (2005).

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using both composite reliability measures and Cronbach's alpha to determine the data's dependability. Table iii shows that all composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values were above .7, falling between .768 and .920, meeting the internal consistency reliability standard of $\alpha \geq .7$ (Hair et al., 2010; Howell et al., 2010). Thus, trustworthiness of internal consistency is established.

Standardized factor loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted were utilized to establish convergence validity (Hair et al., 2017). The average variance extracted values ranged between .650 and .733, falling within the benchmark of $AVE > .6$. The standardized factor loadings ranged between .639 and .933, falling within the benchmark of $SFL > .6$ (Hair et al., 2010). The Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values ranged between .768 and .901, falling within the benchmark of $\alpha \geq .7$ (Howell et al., 2010). Convergence validity was thus attained since every threshold for each indicator used to assess convergence validity was reached (Hair et al., 2014; 2019).

Discriminant validity was measured using square roots of AVE as well as the maximum shared variance (MSV) (Alumran et al., 2014; Segars, 1997). Table iv shows the measurement of discriminant validity using the two metrics.

Table 4. Measurement of Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	CT	PT	ST	RT	CUT	PR	CHE	MSE	DA	AP
CT	.920	.712	.295	.925	.844									
PT	.811	.733	.331	.820	.327	.856								
ST	.847	.692	.327	.851	.155	.163	.832							
RT	.861	.664	.286	.872	.317	.375	.061	.815						
CUT	.827	.692	.277	.830	.144	.301	.227	.194	.832					
PR	.844	.661	.291	.855	.319	.093	.103	.261	.107	.813				
DA	.850	.691	.330	.866	.398	.178	.325	.217	.188	.087	.244	.109	.831	
AP	.794	.704	.319	.801	.351	.277	.116	.287	.305	.241	.137	.225	.091	.839

Key: CR - Composite reliability; AVE - Average variance extracted; MSV - Maximum shared variance; MaxR (H) - Maximum reliability.

Table iv shows that the square roots of AVE (bold diagonal values) are greater than corresponding inter-construct correlations. This demonstrates the presence of discriminant validity in the data (Segars, 1997). Also, using the MSV, the results in Table iv show that the values of AVE are greater than the MSV values, again, demonstrating the presence of discriminant validity in the data (Alumran et al., 2014).

Hypothesis Testing

AMOS version 22 was used in the structural equation modeling (SEM) method of testing hypotheses. Prior to use SEM for hypothesis testing, a study of model fit metrics was carried out to determine if the metrics fell within the allowed range for structural equation modeling (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Hooper et al., 2009; Kline, 2005). The model fit metrics also called the modified measurement assessment indices which

were analyzed were (i) the absolute fit metrics namely, the Chi-square value/degree of freedom (χ^2 /df), goodness of fit index (GFI) and adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI) (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Reisinger & Mavondo, 2007); (ii) the incremental fit metrics namely, normed fit indices (NFI), and the Tucker Lewis index (TLI) also called the Non-normed fit index (NNFI) (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Marsh, Balla & McDonald, 1988), and (iii) the parsimonious fit metrics namely, the comparative fit index (CFI), and the Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) (Browne & Cudeck, 1993; Hu & Bentler, 1998; Stieger, 1990).

For measurement model fit to be deemed acceptable, the measurement metrics should satisfy the following benchmarks: $\chi^2 /df < 3.000$; $TLI > .9000$; $NFI > .9000$; $GFI > .9000$; and $AGFI > .9000$; and $.0600 \leq RMSEA \leq .0800$ (Byrne, 1998; Hooper et al., 2008; Kline, 2005; Reisinger & Mavondo, 2007; McQuitty & Wolf, 2013).

Table 5. Measurement Model Assessment Using Model Fit Indices

Model fit measures	Model fit indices	Initial model measurement	Modified model measurement	Recommended values	Sources
Absolute fit measures	χ^2 /df	2.619	2.377	≤ 3.000	Hooper et al. (2008), Kline (2005), Reisinger and Mavondo (2007)
	GFI	.871	.963	$\geq .950$	
	AGFI	.885	.972	$\geq .900$	
Incremental fit Measures	NFI	.919	.968	$\geq .950$	Hooper et al. (2008), Kline (2005), Reisinger and Mavondo (2007)
	TLI	.961	.981	$\geq .950$	
Parsimonious fit measures	CFI	.895	.933	$\geq .900$	Hooper et al. (2008), Kline (2005), Reisinger and Mavondo (2007)
	RMSEA	.069	.047	$< .080$	

The results of the measurement model assessment in Table v shows that in the initial model measurement, most of the indices did not meet the minimum benchmark required for model fit. However, after the outliers were removed during data cleaning, a re-assessment of the indices was done and modified model fit values were determined. All the modified model measurement were above the minimum recommended values ($\chi^2/df = 2.377$; $GFI = .963$; $AGFI = .972$; $NFI = .968$; $TLI = .981$; $CFI = .933$; and $RMSEA = .047$) hence demonstrated all the fit indices were of acceptable levels hence path analysis using structural equation modelling was performed to test hypotheses (Hooper et al., 2008; Kline, 2005; Reisinger & Mavondo, 2007).

Table 6. Path Analysis on Hypothesized Relationships

Hypotheses	DV	Path	IV	Unstandardized estimates	SE	P	Standardized estimates	R ²
H1	DA	←	CT	.485	.051	.001	.627	.441
H2	DA	←	PT	.217	.062	.000	.409	.369
H3	DA	←	ST	.501	.045	.010	.614	.554
H4	DA	←	RT	.262	.030	.002	.391	.381
H5	DA	←	CUT	.138	.072	.005	.260	.337
H6	DA	←	PR	.416	.056	.009	.519	.504

Key: DV - Dependent variable; IV - Independent variable; SE - Standard error; P - significant level; R² - Coefficient of determination; Significant level - .05

The results in Table vi, also highlighted in Figure ii below, show that all the latent variables had a significant influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of Mathematics at O' level.

Figure 2. Path Analysis Structure for Dialogue and Argumentation Factors

It is shown in Table vi and as also shown in Figure ii that collective teaching (CT) has a significant and positive influence ($\beta = .627$; $p = .001$; $p < .05$; $R^2 = .441$) on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. The results in Table 6 also show that collective teaching contributes 44.1% variation in the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. This therefore speaks to the importance of activities such as group work in assisting students in the effective learning of Mathematics.

The results in Table vi also showed that purposeful teaching (PT) has a significant influence ($\beta = .409$; $p = .000$; $p < .05$; $R^2 = .339$) on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. The results also show that purposeful teaching contributes 33.9% variation to the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

Table vi show that there is a significant and positive relationship between supportive teaching (ST) and effective application of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics ($\beta = .614$; $p = .010$; $p < .05$; $R^2 = .554$). The results in Table iv also show that supportive teaching contributes 55.4% variation to the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

The results in Table vi also show that reciprocal teaching (RT) has a significant and positive influence ($\beta = .391$, $p = .002$; $p < .05$; $R^2 = .381$) on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. The results in Table 4.8 also show that reciprocal teaching contributes 38.1% variation to the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

It is shown in Table vi that cumulative teaching (CUT) has a significant and positive influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics ($\beta = .260$; $p = .005$; $p < .05$; $R^2 = .337$). The results in Table 4.5 also show that cumulative teaching contributes 33.7% variation to the effective use of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

The results in Table vi as also highlighted in Figure ii show that pedagogical repertoire has a significant and positive influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics ($\beta = .519$, $p = .009$, $p < .05$; $R^2 = .504$). In terms of variation contribution, the results of the study as shown in Table iv show that pedagogical repertoire contributes 50.4% of the variation to the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

Discussion

This purpose of the study was to establish factors that have an influence in the teaching of O' level Mathematics using the dialogue and argumentation approach. The results of the study revealed collective teaching (CT) has a significant influence on the teaching of O' level Mathematics using the dialogue and argumentation approach. Collective teaching (CT) provides students with the opportunities to discuss, problem solve, create solutions and work with others. This suggests that when students are provided with opportunities to work in groups and collaborate as allowed for by the dialogue and argumentation approach, they learn Mathematics better. This is consistent with the study by Cervantes-Barraza et al. (2020) that found that promotion of collaborative learning as allowed for by the dialogue and argumentation approach in Mathematics class was an opportunity to encourage students who do not participate in Mathematics discussion.

It was established in the study that purposeful teaching (PT) has significant influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. This suggests that purposeful teaching (PT) helps students to find mathematical meaning from the mathematical content. A study by Davidson and Edwards-Groves (2017) found that the nature and influence of pedagogy in Mathematics classrooms as allowed for by purposeful teaching (PT) is comprehensively and consistently dependent on the dialogic patterns at play in the sequential flow of teacher-student exchanges in Mathematics lessons. This suggests that the use of strategic prompts as allowed for by purposeful teaching influences the effective use of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics.

It also emerged from the study that there is a significant and positive relationship between supportive teaching (ST) and effective application of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. These results suggest that for the effective use of supportive teaching during dialogue and argumentation, teachers should ensure effective interactions of students during the teaching and learning process. The above results are consistent with results of previous studies. A study by Hennessy et al. (2019) found that students need support and scaffolding in their interaction in the classroom in order to enhance their thinking and understanding of mathematical concepts. This is also confirmed in an earlier study by Alexander (2017), which revealed that the teacher has a vital role in facilitating, scaffolding and creating effective learning experiences for students.

It is established from the results that reciprocal teaching (RT) has a significant and positive influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. This suggests that two way reciprocal teaching (RT) nurture in-depth understanding of the mathematical concepts. A study by Muhonen (2018) showed that if students are provided with opportunities for reciprocal learning, they are able to demonstrate deep reasoning and ability to demonstrate their thoughts and answers as part of learning Mathematics. This was also confirmed in earlier studies on the application of reciprocal teaching (RT) of Mathematics. Studies by Guadian et al. (2016) and Atanga et al. (2017) who both found that reciprocal teaching enables teachers to create opportunities for students to share their mathematical thinking with each other in a manner that enhances better understanding of mathematical concepts.

It was shown in the study that cumulative teaching (CUT) has a significant and positive influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. This suggests that teachers need to allow students to build on their own and each other ideas and chain them into coherent lines of thinking and understanding during Mathematics learning. A study by Lee (2016) found that cumulative teaching (CUT) helps students to more effectively engage with as well as link previously learned mathematical concepts with current mathematical concepts the teacher would have exposed them to.

It further emerged from the study that pedagogical repertoire has a significant and positive influence on the effectiveness of dialogue and argumentation in the teaching of O' level Mathematics. This suggests that pedagogical repertoire gives teachers a host of strategies, activities, and techniques to use in the teaching and learning Mathematics using the dialogue and argumentation approach. This is consistent with the study by Alexander (2017) that found that Mathematics teachers who have a pedagogical

repertoire have the ability to develop in their students' confidence to tell and explain, ask different relevant questions, explore ideas, clearly articulate their responses as well as frame meaningful opinions and judgements on mathematical situations they will be dealing with.

Conclusions

It was concluded that all the factors of dialogue and argumentation namely: collective teaching, purposeful teaching, supportive teaching, reciprocal teaching, cumulative teaching and pedagogical repertoire had a significant influence on the academic performance of ordinary level mathematics students. Based on these results, it was then concluded that the dialogue and argumentation strategy has a positive influence on academic performance of ordinary level mathematics students in Zimbabwe.

Recommendations

A number of recommendations were made based on the results of the study. The following recommendations are therefore important for ensuring enhanced academic performance of students in ordinary level mathematics:

- i) Ensuring that the teacher acts as a full partner in discussions with students in Mathematics lessons.
- ii) Setting lesson objectives that allow students to engage in critical thinking rather than in simple one-word answers.
- iii) Allowing students freely articulate their ideas during Mathematics lessons.
- iv) Creating opportunities for the teacher and students listen to one another during Mathematics lessons.
- v) Allowing students to build on their own and others' ideas during Mathematics lessons.

Implications of the Study

There is need for the curriculum materials to be created and implemented in conjunction with dialogue and argumentation teaching methodologies to foster the growth of conceptual knowledge in Mathematics. There is also need to train Mathematics teachers on how to plan and implement the dialogue and argumentation teaching approach in the Mathematics classroom.

Study Limitations

The main study limitation was that the findings of this study might not be transferable nationally since the study was delimited to only schools in Gutu district of Masvingo province in Zimbabwe.

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